

ASSESSMENT OF CLINICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF PREMATURE PLACENTAL ABNORMALITY IN WOMEN AT RISK

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ABSTRACT

Premature separation of a normally situated placenta (PSP) remains one of the most severe obstetric pathologies, posing a significant threat to the life and health of both mother and fetus. The aim of this study was to evaluate the clinical and morphological factors contributing to the development of PSP in women at risk. The material was based on data from a comprehensive clinical and morphological study of 47 women diagnosed with PSP. The control group consisted of women with a normal pregnancy and delivery. Morphological examination of the placentas revealed a number of typical changes: areas of extensive intervillous hemorrhage, destruction and fibrinoid necrosis of the trophoblast, pronounced vascular spasm, and endothelial dystrophy. Increased hyalinosis and fibrosis in the chorionic villi, multiple foci of ischemia and necrosis were noted. The data obtained confirm that premature detachment of a normally located placenta is a multifactorial process, rooted in impaired vascular adaptation and degenerative changes in the placental tissue. A comprehensive clinical and morphological assessment allows for the identification of high-risk women and the implementation of timely preventive measures aimed at preserving the pregnancy and preventing obstetric complications..

Study objective:

To evaluate clinical and morphological factors contributing to the development of premature detachment of a normally located placenta in women at risk

Materials and methods

The study is based on an analysis of 47 cases of premature placental abruption observed in women aged 21 to 39 years at risk. The control group consisted of 20 women with normal pregnancies and deliveries. Clinical data included the results of the obstetric history, laboratory tests, and instrumental examinations (ultrasound, Doppler ultrasound, coagulation profile). Morphological examination was performed on placental samples obtained after delivery using standard histological methods and hematoxylin and eosin staining.

Study results

Clinical features: Among the women examined, patients with complicated pregnancies predominated: arterial hypertension was detected in 20 (42.5%), preeclampsia in 17 (36.2%), anemia of pregnancy in 13 (27.6%), and chronic inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs in 14 (29.7%) women. Fifteen (31.9%) patients were over 30 years of age. In 18 women (38.3%), signs of placental insufficiency were registered (according to Doppler ultrasound data, a decrease in the resistance index of the uterine arteries, impaired uteroplacental blood flow. In 11 cases (23.4%), PONRP was combined with hemostatic disorders and a tendency to hypercoagulation. Of the morphological changes in the placenta, the following changes were found, since macroscopically the placentas were distinguished by a decrease in mass and thickness, the presence of areas of hemorrhage and retroplacental hematomas. Microscopically, extensive intervillous hemorrhages and ruptures of the chorionic villi were revealed; severe spasm and dystrophic changes in blood vessels, fibrinoid degeneration of the trophoblast and hyalinosis of the villous stroma, signs of ischemia and focal necrosis of placental tissue, an increase in the number of macrophages and lymphoid infiltrates in the intervillous space. The results obtained confirm the multifactorial nature of premature placental abruption, where vascular and trophoblastic disorders developing against a background of chronic hypoxia and inflammation play a key role. The combination of systemic factors—hypertension, preeclampsia, anemia—with local morphological changes (vascular spasm, villous destruction, and fibrinoid degeneration) creates conditions for impaired microcirculation and retroplacental hemorrhage, leading to placental abruption.

Premature detachment of a normally located placenta in women at risk is caused by a combination of systemic vascular, inflammatory, and metabolic disorders. The morphological structure of the placenta in PPD is characterized by ischemic, necrotic, and fibrinoid changes in the chorionic villi, as well as signs of chronic inflammation. Clinical and morphological assessment of the placenta allows for the identification of high-risk women and the implementation of differentiated preventive measures to reduce the incidence of obstetric complications.

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